

Supplementary material: Scalable production of solid-immersion lenses for quantum emitters in silicon carbide

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1 Experimental setup

Figure 1: Hanbury, Brown Twiss interferometer used during the measurements.

A home-built confocal microscope setup with a 660 nm diode laser for V_{Si} excitation and an air-objective lens with a numerical aperture (NA)=0.85 (sketched in Fig. 1). The two detectors employed are two photon counting avalanche photodiode modules (APD). The fluorescence was detected with a 830 nm long pass filter.

2 Spectrum of single vacancies center in SiC

Fig.2 shows the spectrum of the single defect under the SIL presented in the main text. The spectrum was recorded with a QEPro Series Ocean Optics spectrometer specific for infrared signal.

3 Optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR)

Radio frequency (RF) signal was generated by a Rohde and Schwarz vector signal generator, subsequently amplified and applied to the V_{Si} in SIL through a 25 μ copper wire.

4 Statistics of enhancement of individual SILs

Table 1 lists the measured enhancement of single emitters located in manufactured SILs, analysed and plotted in figure 3a in the main text.

Figure 2: Spectrum taken with 830 nm longpass filter.

2,3	2,1	2,2	2,9	2,0
2,4	1,6	1,8	1,9	2,8
2,3	2,6	2,0	1,8	2,2
2,4	1,4	1,5	1,8	3,0
2,8	2,8	3,1	2,9	1,3
1,0	2,8	1,0	1,4	1,3
2,4	1,6	2,2	1,5	2,6
1,5	2,5	2,9	1,9	1,4
2,7	1,8	1,6	1,8	1,6
1,9	1,5	1,3	3,4	

Table 1: 49 measurements included in the statistical studies